

RESISTANCE OF THE FAMILY AND LINES OBTAINED AS A RESULT OF INTERGENOME HYBRIDIZATION TO VARIOUS WILT RACES

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Introduction. The greatest damage to the crop, the technological properties of cotton fiber is caused by the verticillium wilt, to which many industrial and newly created varieties quickly lose sustainability. It is generally accepted that the reasons for the rapid loss resistance of new varieties are permanent monoculture, accumulation of the mass of the pathogen in the soil, mechanical damage to the roots and, to a large extent, genetic affinity zoned varieties. According to many authors, only the creation and introduction of varieties on a new genetic basis can, to some extent, solve the problem of increasing resistance cotton to the disease. One of the ways to solve the problem of morbidity of the created varieties is to involve in the breeding process donors of resistance obtained with the participation of wild species.

According to the results, the highest infestation rate was Namangan-77, which was a control variety, with a total infestation rate of 36.8% and a strong 16.8%. Infection with wilt varieties Tashkent-6 and C-6524 was 19.1% and 28.6%, respectively, and to a greater extent 7.1% and 10%. Among the families and lines studied, the lowest infection was observed in families O-117-125 / 18 and O-87-91 / 18, with a total infection rate of 10.5% and a strong infection rate of 2.5-3.5%. formed. This indicates the complete dominance of families and lines obtained by intergenomic hybridization over standard varieties. It is also noted that families O-142-147 / 18 (21.8%), T-1306 (25.2%), O-132-141 / 18 (29.5%) have a relatively high level of wilting as already mentioned, the overall infection rate was in the range of 20-30% (table).

Table. 1

Affection of wilt complete interspecies, bekkross hybrids and conventional varieties to compare their stability, %

№	Families and lineas	Varieties and hybrids	At the overall degree %		At the strong degree %	
			M±m	V,%	M±m	V,%

1.	O-142-147/18	F ₁₀ (F ₁ K- 28 x C-4727) x Oмад	21,8±3, 1	45, 2	4,8±0, 9	15, 4
2.	O-107-116/18	--/--	20,4±2, 3	38, 7	6,2±1, 3	18, 6
3.	O-160-171/18	F ₁₀ (F ₁ K-28 x C-6524)	18,3±1, 9	29, 3	3,6±0, 8	12, 4
4.	O-117-125/18	F ₉ {BC ₂ [(F ₁ K-28 x C-6524) x Oмад] x Oмад}	10,5±1, 4	27, 8	2,5±0, 4	10, 2
5.	O-132-141/18	F ₁₀ (F ₁ K- 28 x C-4727)	29,5±4, 0	48, 6	7,5±1, 0	21, 2
6.	O-201-204/18	P. 169-176(2013)	13,4±1, 7	25, 4	3,4±0, 7	15, 4
7.	O-312-313/18	F ₁₀ (F ₁ K- 28 тип arbor.) x Oмад	17,2±1, 9	26, 8	3,8±0, 6	16, 5
8.	O-87-91/18	F ₉ {BC ₂ [(F ₁ K-28 x C-6524) x Oмад] x Oмад}	10,5±1, 0	22, 1	3,5±0, 5	12, 1
9.	T-1306	F ₈ [BC ₁ (F ₁ K- 28 x C-4727) x Oмад]	25,2±2, 9	46, 3	7,2±0, 9	21, 3
10.	T-1379	F ₁₂ {BC ₁ [(F ₁ K-28 x C-6524) x Oмад]	14,5±1, 6	23, 2	4,1±0, 6	20, 2
11.	СП-1303	F ₆ [(F ₁ K-28 x C-4727) x Oмад] x Oмад	17,5±2, 8	26, 5	5,4±0, 8	21, 5
12.	C-4727	Control variety	36,8 ±4,7	54, 1	16,8 ±1,7	35, 4
13.	C-6524 st	Control variety	28,6±1, 8	21, 6	10,1±1 ,2	29, 6
14.	Тошкент-6st	Control variety	19,1±1, 5	16, 8	7,1±0, 9	23, 4

It can be seen that these indicators recorded complete resistance compared to the control cultivar C-4727. It should be noted that the families and lines in which the C-4727 variety is involved in the origin of the families, it can be seen that the damage from the wilt is relatively high. This suggests that the level of Wilt resistance in families is also relatively high under the influence of the C-4727 cultivar genotype, which is not resistant to Wilt disease. But, you can see a positive effect on increasing resistance to wilt Amphidiploid K-28, Amphidiploid [F1 (F1 G. thurberi Tod x G. raimondi Ulbr) x G. arboretum L.].

